

ISic3607

I.Sicily inscription 3607

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

natural rock

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Syracusae

Place of origin (modern)

Siracusa

Provenance

Priolo Gargallo, hypogeum A, contrada Monachella

Coordinates**Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Priolo Gargallo, in situ

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 491421

EDCS 46600162

Bibliography

1888-. *L'année épigraphique: revue des publications épigraphiques relatives a l'antiquité romaine.. L'année épigraphique : revue des publications épigraphiques relatives a l'antiquité romaine..* At 2007.0674

1923-. *Supplementum epigraphicum graecum. Supplementum epigraphicum graecum.* At 57.0901

Bommara, T., Rizzone, V.G. 2007. Contributo alla conoscenza del territorio

siracusano: recenti indagini a Priolo Gargallo. In Bonacasa Carra, R.M., Vitale, E. (eds.), *La cristianizzazione in Italia fra tardoantico e altomedioevo*. Palermo. pp. 1647-1672. At 1659 fig.13

Licensed under a Creative
Commons-Attribution 4.0 licence.

Cite as:

J. Prag et al. (2020-12-23): ISic3607. <http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk>. (Collection: TEI edition). <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4388813>